

SPRINT QUESTIONNAIRE

The project goal remained clear.

We monitored our performance individually and gave feedback.

We had/learned the technical and human skills necessary to achieve our goals.

Our collective goal remained a priority over individual goals.

We trusted each other enough to share insights, information, and feedback.

We strove to improve our performance.

We were given all the resources and conditions necessary to perform the tasks.

If it was necessary to adapt the scope of the project, the group would understand.

We created a safe space for team members to discuss performance issues.

We recognized the contributions of team members.

We understood all the technical problems we faced.

We developed the tasks following the planned order of priority.

We identified and resolved performance issues among team members.